

Effect of Tourism on Economic Wellbeing of Host Communities in Cross River State, Nigeria

Anionwu, Carol Ph.D

Department of Marketing, Faculty of Management Sciences,
Cross River University of Technology, Calabar, Nigeria

How to cite this paper: Anionwu, Carol "Effect of Tourism on Economic Wellbeing of Host Communities in Cross River State, Nigeria" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-3 | Issue-5, August 2019, pp.246-253, <https://doi.org/10.31142/ijtsrd25295>

IJTSRD25295

Copyright © 2019 by author(s) and International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development Journal. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0) (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>)

ABSTRACT

This study examined the effect of tourism on economic wellbeing of host communities in Cross River State, Nigeria. The study modelled the effect of service, product, hotels, transportation and infrastructural facilities on economic well being of host communities in Cross River State. It is a descriptive survey on a sample of 400 respondents from the host communities. Data obtained for the study were analyzed using percentages, mean, standard deviation and regression analysis. From the result of the regression model it was observed that product, service and infrastructure have positive impact on the on the economic well-being of the host communities. This means that if product, service and infrastructure are developed and improved, it will bring about more increase in the economic well-being of the host communities. On the other hand, hotels and transportation have a negative impact on the economic wellbeing of the host communities. Thus, increase in hotels and transportation cost will bring about a decline in the economic wellbeing of the host communities. The overall significance of the model also supports the alternate hypothesis that the model has goodness of fit and is statistically significant. In other words, tourism consumption has significant impact on the economic wellbeing of the host communities. Based on the analysis and findings of the study the following recommendations are made: Since tourism consumption has become imperative for economies to thrive successfully, it is imperative that government should develop and as well as regulate operators in the tourism destination to step up the quality of product, service and infrastructure provided in the tourist destination. This is because they have been found to have positive impact on the on the economic well-being of the host communities. The government should also come up with policy instruments containing measures that will 'effectively' monitor and evaluate the operations of tourism destinations. This is necessary as this research manifest the fact that hotels and transportation cost negatively affects the host communities. In other words it will bring about a decline in the economic wellbeing of the host communities if not regulated.

KEYWORDS: *Tourism, Economic Wellbeing, Service, Product, Hotels, Transportation and Infrastructural Facilities*

1. INTRODUCTION

The economic importance of tourism has been amplified from various stand points and from varying literary perspectives. It has been considered to be one of the world's largest and most dynamic industries (Matiza & Oni, 2014; Surungiu, 2009). Consequently, the economic potentials of tourism to the Gross Domestic Products (GDP) of advanced and emerging economies and even the host communities have escalated research interest and curiosity among scholars and researchers alike. Extant literature reports that tourism has been increasingly seen as an important economic activity and a significant engine of overall development in many destinations. It generates 10% of employment around the world and accounts for 10.4% of global GDP (Zhuang, Yao & Li, 2019; World Travel and Tourism Council, 2018; Lin & Mao, 2015; Pappas, 2014; Ryan, 2003). Eruotor (2014) asserts that tourism is a major force in any economy in the world; it is one sector of the

economy that has a global importance. In this world of globalization where change is constant, tourism tends to improve the economy of the third world countries and also have an impact upon the host community. Tourism is the largest and fastest growing industry in the world. According to Zaei and Zaei (2013), tourism is an economic sector able to offer a significant contribution to the economic growth of a region and to the labour market, and creates occupation opportunities directly and indirectly through the supply of goods and the necessary services for tourist activities. Moreover, tourism produces social benefits to the region (i.e. small and medium-sized enterprises' development, creation of new jobs, improvement of infrastructure etc.). Matiza and Oni (2014) view tourism as a potential growth catalyst for less developed nations and emerging economies. It is also regarded as a poverty alleviation tool given the sectors' labour intensive, inclusive and informal attributes.

Promoting tourism can attract regional investment, create commercial opportunities, and support other industries within a destination area (Zhuang, Yao & Li, 2019). Apart from attracting investment, creating commercial opportunities, and support for other industries within a destination involves huge cost to make the destinations viable, thus making a circular flow of resources within the economy. Stynes (undated) posits that a standard economic impact analysis traces flows of money from tourism spending, first to businesses and government agencies where tourists spend their money and then to other businesses - supplying goods and services to tourist businesses; households - earning income by working in tourism or supporting industries; and government - through various taxes and charges on tourists, businesses and households. Tourism activity also involves economic costs, including the direct costs incurred by tourism businesses, government costs for infrastructure to better serve tourists, as well as congestion and related costs borne by individuals in the community. Community decisions over tourism often involve debates between industry proponents touting tourism's economic impacts (benefits) and detractors emphasizing tourism's costs. Sound decisions rest on a balanced and objective assessment of both benefits and costs and an understanding of who benefits from tourism and who pays for it. Tourism's economic impacts are therefore an important consideration in state, regional and community planning and economic development. Economic impacts are also important factors in marketing and management decisions. Communities therefore need to understand the relative importance of tourism to their region, including tourism's contribution to economic activity in the area (Stynes, undated).

1.1. Objective of the Study

The broad objective of this study is to examine the effect of tourism on economic wellbeing of host communities in Cross River State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study modelled the effect of service, product, hotels, transportation and infrastructural facilities on economic wellbeing of host communities in Cross River State.

1.2. Research Hypothesis

H₀₁: Tourism has no significant impacts on economic wellbeing of host communities in Cross River State.

2. RELATED EMPIRICAL LITERATURE

This section x-rays related empirical literature on the effect of tourism on economic wellbeing of host communities. Researchers have approached the study area from different standpoints and from varying literary perspectives. For example, Spanou (2010) examined the impact of tourism on the socio-cultural structure of Cyprus using descriptive statistics. The study revealed that in spite of all the negative and positive impacts of tourism on Cyprus it is not yet clear whether the benefits outweigh the costs. The reason for this uncertainty is that most of the research is done on an estimate as there is no empirical data available as yet to support either side of the equation. However, it also revealed that the residents of Cyprus have a positive attitude toward tourism. Since the success of tourism depends very much on the human factor, i.e. the attitudes and behaviour of the residents of a destination towards tourists, this seems to be an encouraging result for the future of tourism development. Residents recognize a range of potential positive and negative impacts of tourism. However, current attitudes are

generally quite positive and there is support for future modest increase in tourism. Ogbu, Idris and Ijagbemi (2011) examined information and communication technology (ICT): A veritable tool for tourism development in Nigeria using descriptive statistics and secondary data from UNWTO technical manual of various issues. Findings revealed that almost every tourism products can be sold online without the consumer necessarily visiting the place before making any choices. Booking of flights and hotel reservations can be done online through e-mail, telephone calls and other internet services thereby helping to reduce if not remove entirely the time wasting processes of the old system. Enemuo and Oduntan (2012) investigated the social impact of tourism development on host communities of Osun Oshogbo Sacred Grove. Simple frequency percentages, mean and Analysis of variance (ANOVA) derived from regression analysis were used to analyse the data generated for the study. The findings of the analysis proved that tourism development had significant effect on the social lives of the host communities and tourism development had significant effect on the sustainability of the socio-cultural lives of the host communities. Zaei and Zaei (2013) analysed the impact of tourism industry on host communities. They posit that tourism is one of the dynamic economic activities in creating socio - economic changes across the world which has been increasingly important. The tourism sector is probably the only service sector that provides concrete and quantified trading opportunities for all nations, regardless of their level of development. However, it is also a sector where there is clearly an uneven distribution of benefits, which is threatening the social, economic and environmental sustainability of tourism in some developing countries. For many developing countries, tourism is one of fundamental pillars of their development process because it is one of the dominant activities in the economy, while for others, particularly by islands and some small economies, it is the only source of foreign currency and employment, and therefore constitutes the platform for their economic development. Amissah (2013) investigated tourist satisfaction with hotel services in Cape Coast and Elmina, Ghana using the gap model. The results revealed four main factors which influence tourists' satisfaction with hotel services. Also, there was a significant relationship between satisfaction and revisit intentions. Matiza and Oni (2014) examined the perceived economic benefits of tourism: the case of a rural community bordering the Kruger National Park in Limpopo Province, South Africa using descriptive data presented in tabular form summarising frequencies and cumulative frequencies per statement. The study found that the community perceived itself to be benefitting economically from tourism activities, albeit the associated costs that could be attributed to tourism activities. Job creation, infrastructural development and improved standards of living were identified as key benefits for the rural populace, while social issues such prostitution were the perceived costs of tourism in the area adjacent to the Kruger National Park of Limpopo Province South Africa. Enemuo and Amaechi (2015) examined the role of mass media in tourism development in Abia State using descriptive statistics. Findings from the study revealed that National War Museum at Umuahia was the most visited tourism destination in Abia State with 56.8% of all the interviewed tourists having visited it. Wonder tree in Amakama was the second most visited destination. Yusuff and Akinde (2015) investigated tourism development and economic growth nexus: Nigeria's experience using the VECM regression

method and data spanning from 1995 to 2013. The findings reveal a unilateral causality and positive long-run between tourism development and economic growth. The tourism-led growth is also thus confirmed for Nigeria. Kalantzi, Tsiotas and Polyzos (2016) examined the contribution of tourism in national economies: evidence of Greece using descriptive and inferential statistic like tables, charts, t-test statistics and Pearson's bivariate correlations. At the period, the available data (2000-2012) two events of the recent Greek history are distinguished as the most significant (the Olympic Games in the year 2004 and the economic crisis initiated in the year 2009) and their impact on the diachronic evolution in tourism is discussed. Findings revealed that under an overall assessment, the analysis illustrated that tourism is a sector of the Greek economy, which is described by a significant resilience. However, it seems that it has not yet been submitted to an effective developmental plan exploiting the endogenous tourism dynamics of the country. This suggests currently a promising investment of "low risk" for the economic growth of country and the exit of the economic crisis. Boz and Karakas (2017) examined the impact of tourism industry on host communities: Antalya and Canakkale cases using a quantitative research technique. The study revealed that there are significant differences between perception and attitudes of local people who live in Antalya and Canakkale. The development of tourism increases the desire of people to learn a foreign language and to become acquainted with foreign cultures. Tourism improves social life of host communities, and contributes women in participating to labour force. The tourism industry provides a positive contribution to the solution of unemployment problem. Liu and Li (2018) examined host perceptions of tourism impact and stage of destination development in a developing country- Puri and Varanasi, India using descriptive statistics and t-test statistics. They collected valid responses from 570 local residents, who displayed a high level of agreement concerning the positive economic and socio-cultural contributions of tourism. Despite environmental concerns, respondents wish to attract more tourists and further develop infrastructure for tourism. Residents who perceive tourism to be in the development and full development/stagnation stages agree more strongly than those who consider tourism to be in the beginning stage that it increases employment opportunities and seasonality and stipulates cultural activities. In contrast, those who think tourism is in the beginning stage are more concerned about environmental pollution and thus advocate restrictions on the industry. Khandare & Phophueksanand (2018) examined the social and cultural impact of tourism development in Thailand using chi-square statistics. Findings showed that the impact on tourism development in Bangkok was different according to the domicile. Statistically significant at the .05 level by the sample with 60.3 percent of resident's of Bangkok that has an impact on the environment. Samples with different domiciles were 40.8 percent that have an impact on the environment. In case the comments about the problems and obstacles to tourism development. No differences between the groups domicile statistically significant at the .05 level. There are different levels of education statistically significant at the .05 level by samples with low education degree, 57.1 percent agreed that tourism development has a major economic impact on the economy. Samples with a bachelor's degree, 50.6 percent agreed that tourism development with environmental effects and samples with a master's degree or higher, 41.7 percent agreed that tourism development affects lifestyle change.

In the final analysis, available literature has shown that tourism has contributed a lot to the development and growth of economies and host communities alike. However, a cursory look at the studies examined so far reveals a literature and knowledge gap that rests on a tripod stand. First, the study revealed that in spite of all the negative and positive impacts of tourism on host communities, it is not yet clear whether the benefits outweigh the costs. Second, most of the studies on tourism focused on socio-cultural impact of tourism on host communities and other aspect of tourism but there seems to be a paucity of research on the effect of tourism on economic wellbeing of host communities. More related studies are the studies carried out by Matiza and Oni (2014) on the perceived economic benefits of tourism: the case of a rural community bordering the Kruger National Park in Limpopo Province, South Africa; Yusuff and Akinde (2015) that investigated tourism development and economic growth nexus in Nigeria and Kalantzi, Tsiotas and Polyzos (2016) that examined the contribution of tourism in national economies: evidence of Greece. The studies carried out by Yusuff and Akinde (2015) and Kalantzi, Tsiotas and Polyzos (2016) made use of aggregate data thus suggesting that their findings reflects on tourism impact on national economies. A more related study was the study carried out by Matiza and Oni (2014) but the study was carried out in Kruger National Park in Limpopo Province, South Africa. Third, none of the studies uses the Tourism consumption activities or indicators to measure the effect of tourism on economic wellbeing of host communities particularly in Cross River State, Nigeria.

3. ETHODOLOGY

3.1. Research Design

This study adopts a descriptive survey research design. Descriptive survey research design can be quantitative or qualitative, but this study is quantitative in nature. According to Micheal, Oparaku and Oparaku (2012), in a quantitative survey research design, the researcher's aim is to determine the relationship between the independent variables and dependent variable in a population. Quantitative research design is either descriptive (variables usually measured once) or experimental (variables measured before and after a treatment). The questions asked are to elicit responses that will answer the research questions and address the objectives of the research.

3.2. Population of the Study

The unit of analysis/defined population for the study is made up all individuals that constitute host communities who themselves may be also the stakeholders. They are also the beneficiaries (positive or negative) of the outcome of Tourism consumption activities for this study the unit of analysis of this study is finite. In the present study the population are drawn from three tourist zones (Calabar Municipal local Government Area, Obudu Local Government Area and Odukpani Local Government Area) in Cross River state. According to the National Population Commission of Nigeria the population of the catchment areas are: Odukpani LGA: 179,392, Obudu LGA: 186,650 and Calabar: 222,980 respectively. The population is finite (that is it is known) because the researcher was able to obtain the estimate of the total population of the catchment areas for the study which came to 589,022.

Table 1: Host Communities

Name of Societies	Population of the Host Communities	Sample Size
Odukpani LGA	179,392	122
Obudu LGA	186,650	127
Calabar LGA	222,980	151
Total	589,022	400

Source: computation from field survey, 2016

To determine the sample size, for the purpose of questionnaire distribution; the Taro Yamani formula was used.

The formula is stated as thus:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where:

n = Sample size

N = Population

E = Margin error (5% or 0.05)

I = Constant

Substituting in the above formula:

$$\begin{aligned} N &= \frac{589,022}{1+589,022(0.05)^2} \\ &= \frac{589,022}{1+589,022(0.0025)^2} \\ &= \frac{589,022}{1473,555} \\ &= 399.7 \\ &\approx 400 \end{aligned}$$

For the purpose of allocation of sample stratum, the researcher adopted R. Kumaisons (1997) formula. Below is the R. Kumaisons formula for sample size distribution:

$$nh = \frac{nN}{N}$$

Where

n = Total sample size

Nh = The number of items in each stratum in the population

N = Population size

nh = The number of units allocated to each stratum

n = 400

Substituting in the above formula for the purpose of allocating the questionnaire to the host communities, we have:

$$\text{Odukpani; } = > nh = \frac{400 \times 179,392}{589,022} = 121.8 = 122$$

$$\text{Odubu; } = > n = \frac{400 \times 186,650}{589,022} = 126.8 = 127$$

$$\text{Calabar; } = > nh = \frac{400 \times 222,980}{589,022} = 151.4 = 151$$

3.3. Sources of Data

Both primary and secondary sources of data were employed by the researcher for this study. Secondary sources were made up of published works by other authors closely related to the present topic, they include: books, professional journals, business and government reports. Primary data were generated from the field through the use of structured questionnaires.

3.4. Research Instrument

The major instrument used for this study was the questionnaires which were constructed to tap information from the respondents. The 5 point summative scale the rating scale model questionnaire was adopted. The rating scale is shown as follows;

Table 1: 5 Points Summative Rating Scale Model

0	1	2	3	4
No impact at all	Low impact	Moderate impact	High impact	Very high impact

The questionnaires were designed based on previous empirical studies carried out by researchers on the economic and socio-ecological impact of tourism. Additionally, the preceding researcher adopted some questionnaire items from Brunt and Courtney (1999), Ribeiro, Vareiro, and Remoaldo (2012) in their socio-economic and environmental (SEE) impacts as well as tourist-host interaction studies respectively.

3.5. Method of Data Analysis

The study is concerned with finding the impact of an independent variable (e.g. Tourism, which is deconstructed with sub-variables such as Service, Products, Hotel, Transportation, and Infrastructural Facilities) on dependent variable - Economic Well-Being. Consequently, the researcher used the Regression Analysis of ordinary least square.

3.6. Model Specification

The model for this study incorporates tourism consumption- Service, Product, Hotels, Transportation and Infrastructural Facilities- as independent variables and Economic Well Being as dependent variable. Thus, the model for the study is stated as follows:

The structural form of the model

$$EWB = f(\text{SER, PRO, HOT, TRAN, INF}) \quad (1)$$

The mathematical form of the model

$$EWB = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{SER} + \beta_2 \text{PRO} + \beta_3 \text{HOT} + \beta_4 \text{TRAN} + \beta_5 \text{INF} \quad (2)$$

The econometric form of the model

$$EWB = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{SER} + \beta_2 \text{PRO} + \beta_3 \text{HOT} + \beta_4 \text{TRAN} + \beta_5 \text{INF} + \mu_i \quad (3)$$

Where;

EWB = ECONOMIC WELL BEING

SER = SERVICE

PRO = PRODUCTS

HOT = HOTELS

TRA = TRANSPORTATION

INF = INFRASTRUCTURAL FACILITIES

f = Functional relationship

β_0 = the intercept or the constant

$\beta_1 - \beta_5$ = the co-efficient of the explanatory variables

μ_i = Stochastic error term.

Table 2: Economic a priori expectation

Parameters	Variables		Expected Relationships	Expected Coefficients
	Regressand	Regressor		
β_0		Intercept	(+/-)	$0 < \beta_0 > 0$
β_1	EWB	SER	+	$\beta_1 < 0$
β_2	EWB	PRO	+	$\beta_2 < 0$
β_3	EWB	HOT	+	$\beta_3 < 0$
β_4	EWB	TRA	+	$\beta_4 < 0$
β_5	EWB	INF	+	$\beta_5 < 0$

Source: Researchers compilation

A positive '+' sign indicate that the relationship between the regressor and regressand is direct and move in the same direction i.e. increase or decrease together. On the other hand, a '-' shows that there is an indirect (inverse) relationship between the regressor and regressand i.e. they move in opposite or different direction.

4. DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1. Administration and Collection of Instrument

The total number of questionnaire distributed was 400. This was determined by the sample size of the study. The number returned was a total of 300copies, representing 75% (percent) of number distributed. This shows that the number not returned was 100 (25%). Based the above, the return rate is considered sufficiently high. This is in consonance with 70% return rate benchmark suggested by some researchers for example Kathari, (2011).

4.2. Data Presentation

This data presentation section is divided into two subsections. The first subsection deals with demographic profile of the respondents. The second subsection deals with the presentation of responses on core subject matter.

4.3. Demographic Profile of Respondents

Table 3 gives an overview of the demographic and socioeconomic characteristics of the sample.

Table 3: Demographic profile of the sample

Demographic profile	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Cumulative Percent
Sex/Gender			
Male	180	60.0	60.0
Female	120	40.0	100.0
Age			
18 -25	164	54.7	54.7
26-35	80	26.7	81.3
36-60	56	18.7	100.0
Marital Status			
Single	182	60.7	60.7
Married	118	39.3	100.0
Occupation			
Civil Servant	38	12.7	12.7
Lecturer	19	6.3	19.0
Business/Trading	45	15.0	34.0
Others	198	66.0	100.0
Place of work			
Hotel and Tourism	20	6.7	6.7
Others	280	93.3	100.0
Annual income			
₦1,000 - ₦199,000	207	69.0	69.0
₦200,000- ₦500,000	71	23.7	92.7
₦600,000 - ₦1,000,000	12	4.0	96.7
₦1,100,000 - ₦2,000,000	10	3.3	100.0
Educational Qualification			
OND/WASC	244	81.3	81.3
PGD/First Degree/ HND	16	5.3	86.7
Masters Degree	22	7.3	94.0
PhD	18	6.0	100.0

Source: Field Survey 2016

From table 3, 60.0% of males responded to the questionnaire while 40.0% of the respondents are females. Majority of the respondents, that is 54.7%, are between the ages of 18-25 years. 26.7% of them fall between the ages 26-35 years, while 18.7% of the respondents are between the ages of 36-60 years. The marital status of the respondents revealed that 60.7% of the respondents are single, while 39.3% of the respondents are married.

The same table shows that over 12.7% of the respondents are civil servants, while 6.3% of them are lecturers, 15.0% of the respondents are into business/trading, 66.0% of the respondents are into other forms of businesses. Annual income revealed that 69.0% of the respondents earn between ₦100, 000 - N 199000, 23.7% earn between ₦200000- ₦500000. 4.0% of the respondents earn between ₦600000 - ₦1000000 per annum and 3.3% earn between ₦1100000 - ₦2000000 per annum.

The above figures show that majority of the members of the Host Communities (almost 70%) are low income earners or otherwise referred to the bottom-of-the-pyramid earners. This therefore is the more reason it has become imperative to find out what improvement has come to them through Tourism. Table 2 also indicates that all the respondents had formal education. Majority of the respondents 81.3% had West African School Certificate (WASC)/ Ordinary National Diploma (OND). Only 5.3% had FIRST DEGREE/Higher National Diploma (HND)/ Post Graduate Diploma (PGD). Finally, 7.3% had Masters Degree while 6.0% had Ph.D. Given these statistics, the researcher was delighted to note that a good majority of the respondents had what can be described as acceptable formal educational background which was a plus for the Host Communities. It made it reassuring and made it possible for them to attend to the questions with ease. And indeed they reacted intelligently and satisfactorily to the questionnaire. This was an evidence which showed that they are very much aware and alive to their environment.

4.4. Regression Result

Table 4: The extent to which Tourism Consumption (TC) affects the Economic Well-Being (EWB) of the Host Communities

Model	B	Std. error	T	Sig.
Constant(C)	-.083	.042	-1.950	.052
IMPACT OF PRODUCTS	.389	.039	9.866	.000
IMPACT OF SERVICES	.454	.054	8.458	.000
IMPACT OF HOTELS	-.023	.067	-.340	.734
IMPACT OF TRANSPORTATION	-.036	.052	-.696	.487
IMPACT OF INFRASTRUCTURE	.249	.064	3.878	.000
R	0.973			
R ²	0.946			
Adj. R ²	0.945			
F-statistic	1029.026			0.000

Source: Field Survey 2016

Dependent Variable: ECONOMIC WELL-BEING

In other to evaluate the extent to which Tourism Consumption (TC) affect the Economic Well-Being (EWB) of the Host Communities, the result of the proposed regression model as specified in the methodology was adopted. Table 4 showed the precision of the model which was analyzed using economic a priori criteria and statistical criteria.

4.5. Evaluation based on economic a priori criteria

This subsection is concerned with evaluating the regression results based on a priori (i.e., theoretical) expectations. The sign and magnitude of each variable coefficient is evaluated against theoretical expectations.

From table 4, it is observed that the regression line has a negative intercept as presented by the constant (c) = $-.083$. This means that if all the variables are held constant or fixed (zero), economic wellbeing of the host communities will be valued at $-.083$. Thus, the a-priori expectation is that the intercept could be positive or negative, so it conforms to the theoretical expectation.

It is observed in Table 4 that product, service and infrastructure have positive impact on the on the economic well-being of the host communities. This means that if product, service and infrastructure are developed and improved, it will bring about more increase in the economic well-being of the host communities. On the other hand, hotels and transportation have a negative impact on the economic wellbeing of the host communities. Thus, increase in hotels and transportation services will bring about a decline in the economic wellbeing of the host communities.

4.6. Discussion based on statistical criteria

This subsection applies the R^2 , adjusted R^2 and the f -test to determine the statistical reliability of the estimated parameters. These tests are performed as follows: From our regression result, the coefficient of determination (R^2) is given as 0.946, which shows that the explanatory power of the variables is extremely high and/or strong. This implies that 94.6% of the variations in the economic wellbeing of the host communities are being accounted for or explained by the variations in the development of products, services, hotels, transportation and infrastructure in the host communities. While other independent variables not captured in the model explain just 5.4% of the variations in the economic wellbeing of the host communities. The adjusted R^2 supports the claim of the R^2 with a value of 0.945 indicating that 94.5% of the total variation in the dependent variable (economic wellbeing of the host communities is explained by the independent variables (the regressors)). Thus, this supports the statement that the explanatory power of the variables that is extremely high and strong.

Test of Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Tourism consumption has no significant impact on the economic wellbeing of the host communities.

Table 5: Impact of Tourism Consumption (TC) on the Economic Well-Being (EWB) of the Host Communities

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	366.826	5	73.365	1029.026	.000 ^b
	Residual	20.961	294	.071		
	Total	387.787	299			

A. Dependent Variable: IMPACT ON ECONOMIC

B. Predictors: (Constant), IMPACT OF INFRASTRUCTURE, IMPACT OF PRODUCT, IMPACT OF TRANSPORTATION, IMPACT OF TOURISM, IMPACT OF HOTELS

The F-statistic: The F-test is applied to check the overall significance of the model. The F-statistic is instrumental in verifying the overall significance of an estimated model. In our model the F-statistic is significant at 0.000. We therefore reject H_0 and accept H_1 that the model has goodness of fit and is statistically significant. In other words, tourism consumption has significant impact on the economic wellbeing of the host communities; however this impact is yet to fully reflect on the host community.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study has examined the effect of tourism on economic wellbeing of host communities in Cross River State, Nigeria. The study modelled the effect of service, product, hotels, transportation and infrastructural facilities on economic well being of host communities in Cross River State. From the result of the proposed regression model it was observed that product, service and infrastructure have positive impact on the on the economic well-being of the host communities. This means that if product, service and infrastructure are developed and improved, it will bring about more increase in the economic well-being of the host communities. On the

other hand, hotels and transportation have a negative impact on the economic wellbeing of the host communities. Thus, increase in hotels and transportation cost will bring about a decline in the economic wellbeing of the host communities. The overall significance of the model also supports the alternate hypotheses that the model has goodness of fit and is statistically significant. In other words, tourism consumption has significant impact on the economic wellbeing of the host communities.

Based on the analysis and findings of the study the following recommendations are made: Since tourism consumption has become imperative for economies to thrive successfully, it is imperative that government should develop and as well as regulate operators in the tourism destination to step up the quality of product, service and infrastructure provided in the tourist destination. This is because they have been found to have positive impact on the on the economic well-being of the host communities. The government should also come up with policy instruments containing measures that will 'effectively' monitor and evaluate the operations of tourism destinations. This is necessary as this research manifest the

fact that hotels and transportation cost negatively affects the host communities. In other words it will bring about a decline in the economic wellbeing of the host communities if not regulated.

References

- [1] Amisssah, E. F. (2013). Tourist Satisfaction with Hotel Services in Cape Coast and Elmina, Ghana. *American Journal of Tourism Management*, 2(1A), 26-33.
- [2] Boz, M. & Karakaş, E. (2017). Impact of tourism industry on host communities: Antalya and Canakkale cases. *Researcher: Social Science Studies*, 5(8), 153-170.
- [3] Enemu, O. B. & Amaechi, B. (2015). The Role of Mass Media in Tourism Development in Abia State. *Journal of Tourism, Hospitality and Sports*, 11: 44-49.
- [4] Enemu, O. B. & Oduntan, O. C. (2012). Social Impact Of Tourism Development On Host Communities Of Osun Oshogbo Sacred Grove. *Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 2(6), 30-35.
- [5] Esu, B. B (2015). Transforming the Nigeria tourism industry through tourism entrepreneurial development. *African Journal of Business Management*. 9(15), 569 – 580.
- [6] Kalantzi, O., Tsiotas, D. & Polyzos, S. (2016). The contribution of tourism in national economies: evidence of Greece. *European Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 5(5), 41 – 64.
- [7] Khandare, V. & Phophueksanand, N. (2018). Social and Cultural Impact of Tourism Development in Thailand. *International Journal of Research in Economics and Social Sciences*, 8(2), 877-887.
- [8] Liu, X. & Li, J. (2018). Host perceptions of tourism impact and stage of destination development in a developing country. *Sustainability*, 10: 1-15.
- [9] Matiza, T. & Oni, O. A. (2014). The Perceived Economic Benefits of Tourism: The Case of a Rural Community Bordering the Kruger National Park in Limpopo Province, South Africa. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(20), 322-328.
- [10] Ogbu, S.E., Idris, S. & Ijagbemi, A.B. (2011). Information and communication technology (ICT): A veritable tool for tourism development in Nigeria. A paper presented at Nigeria Computer Society (NCS): 10TH International Conference – July 25-29, 2011.
- [11] Spanou, E. (2010). The impact of tourism on the sociocultural structure of Cyprus. *An International Multidisciplinary Journal of Tourism*, 2(1), 145-162.
- [12] UNWTO (2010) *Tourism Highlight*, 2010 Edition, p. 3. Vavra, T.G. (1997) "Improving Your Measurement of Customer Satisfaction: A Guide to Creating, Conducting, Analyzing and Reporting Customer Satisfaction Measurement Programs, ASQ Quality Press.
- [13] Yusuff, M. A. and Akinde, M. A (2015). Tourism development and economic growth nexus: Nigeria's experience. *European Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Research*, 3(4), 1-10.
- [14] Zaei, M. E. & Zaei, M. E. (2013). The impacts of tourism industry on host community. *European Journal of Tourism Hospitality and Research*, 1(2), 12-21.

